

Gender Inclusive Tourism in Hyderabad: A Quantitative Analysis

Tuhina Sinha (Assistant Professor)¹

¹Department of Urban and Regional Planning, SPA,
JNAFAU, Hyderabad

Dr. S. Kumar (Professor)²

²SPA, JNAFAU, Hyderabad

Dr. V.V. HaraGopal(Professor)³

³Department of Statistics, Osmania University, Hyderabad

Abstract:- The growing influence of the tourism sector as an economic powerhouse and its potential as a tool for development is indisputable. Tourism apart from spearheading growth also improves the quality of people's lives with its capacity to create large-scale employment of diverse kinds. It is one of the most labor-intensive sectors of the economy and therefore plays a crucial role in providing opportunities for low-skilled workers, ethnic minority groups and migrants, unemployed youth, long-term unemployed, as well as women. Tourism is an important source of employment for women, especially in developing countries, but with profound limitations and focuses on low-level, low-paid, and precarious jobs. Despite the significant growth of tourism, research suggests a widening gap in tourism planning from a gender perspective (limited accessibility, mobility, safety, security, and workforce participation). Hence, it is important to address this exclusivity in tourism from a gender's perspective. This paper attempts to examine the correlation between gender inclusiveness and tourism development through quantitative analysis by highlighting the key findings to draw conclusions and insights.

Keywords:- Gender Inclusive Cities, Inclusive Planning, Gender Mainstreaming, Tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

As one of the world's largest economic sectors, tourism creates jobs, drives exports, and generates prosperity across the world. According to the global economic impact of Travel & Tourism (WTTC 2018), the sector is shown to account for 10.4% of the global GDP and 313 million jobs, or 9.9% of total employment, in 2017. Tourism, in India, has emerged as a booming industry and has witnessed tremendous growth in the last few years. It contributes 6.23 percent to the national GDP and 8.78% of the total employment in India. The Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) in India continued to grow from 1.28 million in 1981 to 1.68 million in 1991, 2.54 million in 2001, and 6.31 million in 2011 to reach 2.74 million in 2020 with foreign exchange earnings at ₹ 211661crore in 2019, while, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) in FTAs in India during 2001 to 2020 was 8.45%. (India Tourism Statistics, Ministry of Tourism, GoI, 2021). The potential of the

tourism industry to contribute to economic and social development has also been recognized in a number of SDGs 8 and 12 (ILO, 2016). Apart from the manifold benefits that accrue from tourism, it has a unique capacity to create large-scale employment of diverse kinds as it provides opportunities for marginalized groups including low-skilled workers, ethnic minority groups and migrants, unemployed youth, long-term unemployed, as well as women. Tourism is an important source of employment for women, especially in developing countries, but with profound limitations and focuses on low-level, low-paid, and precarious jobs. (UNWTO & UN Women, 2011). The major challenge is to increase the development of tourism from a gender perspective. Hence, addressing gender inequality as a prerequisite for sustainable, inclusive, and resilient tourism globally becomes imperative.

➤ Background

Globally, the current state of gender equality depicts a significant regional variation in pay with women typically earning 10-15% less than their male counterparts according to key findings of the Global Report on Women in Tourism 2010. The International Labour Organisation in 2013, commissioned Thomas Baum to produce the first official report on the situation of women in the hotel trade, catering, and tourism. According to the research, at a global level, women constituted 55.5% of the workforce and accounted for 46% of wage employment in tourism globally (DM: Cross-Cutting Issues and Gender, 2012). The importance of gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls have been underscored in the World Development Report 2012 and the UN (SDG 5). While in India, the female share of the labor force stands at 25% and has a lower share of contribution to GDP (17%) than the global average of 37%, according to the McKinsey Global Institute Report, 2018). India ranks 149th out of 153 countries in the economic gender gap of the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Index 2020. It has further slipped 28 places to rank 140 among 156 countries in the Global Gender Gap Report, 2021. Women accounted for a little under half (33.73 percent) of India's total urban population in 2011 (377.1 million) Census, 2011. The urban sex ratio is quite skewed, it was 926 females per 1,000 males, compared to an all-India (940 females per 1,000 males). Therefore, globally and nationally, all policies recognize and emphasize the need for

an inclusive urban society. While Tourism has the unique ability to ensure that nobody is left behind.

➤ *Purpose of Study*

The aim of the study is “to examine the key factors affecting gender inequities in tourism for the case of Hyderabad.” It attempts to explore the correlation between gender inclusiveness and tourism by providing quantitative analysis and highlighting the key findings. The main objective is to identify and establish the parameters for the assessment of gender sensitivity in tourism. With the framed objectives, the primary data is collected by designing a questionnaire for 41 experts, 211 visitors, and 63 stakeholders. The data collected was primarily ordinal and divided into three parts which are summarized with multivariate test statistics i.e. Factor analysis was carried out to finalize the components that would represent the number of attributes on which the data is collected. The study would confine to gender issues (social, economic, environmental) in tourism within Hyderabad and therefore is a purposive study that discusses the needs of women and girls within tourism. The following tasks have been undertaken for the study-

- Data collection was carried out in three parts, first with the help of a structured online survey questionnaire (Expert Opinion Survey) for the targeted experts with relevant parameters identified from literature studies, second, a structured questionnaire for tourists (Visitors survey), and third Stakeholders survey at the selected sites.
- KMO and Bartlett’s test was conducted to check the reliability and adequacy of the sample by Cronbach’s Alpha.
- A chi-Square test was conducted for the attribute data
- Confirmatory Factor Analysis was conducted to identify the final set of parameters for assessing gender inclusiveness in tourism for the study area.

➤ *Case Study Area*

After the reorganization of Andhra Pradesh, Telangana state came into existence on 2nd June 2014 with a geographical spread of 1, 14,840 sq km making it the 12th largest state in the country, with Hyderabad as its state capital. Hyderabad is the world’s newest megacity, reaching 10 million inhabitants in 2020, and functions as the central administrative, industrial, and commercial hub of the state. From its origin as a small town founded in 1591, it has developed to become one of India’s fastest-growing metropolises with a population of approximately 7.7 million (Census of India., 2011) which is further expected to increase to about 19 million by the year 2041 (GoAP, 2013).

Today Hyderabad by spatial extent is the second largest metropolitan region in India, occupying a land size of about 7228 km² (GoAP, 2013). Above 550m from sea level, the city is characterized by many hillocks and beautiful rock formations found on the Deccan plateau. Several natural water tanks make the city very attractive. Since 1991, Hyderabad has emerged as one of the most populous capital cities and a cosmopolitan city with varied cultures and communities. The city comprises both natural tourism and man-made attractions, due to its rich culture and heritage sites. Domestic visitors in Hyderabad accounted for approximately 1.7 million visits in the fiscal year 2018 (www.statista.com, 2019). Foreign tourist arrivals have increased from 2.33 million in 2016 to 2.71 million in 2017. The 16 selected tourist sites under study were as follows- Monuments/Historical Places including Charminar, Golconda Fort, and Qutub Shahi Tombs, Religious Places including Birla Mandir, Chilkur Balaji Temple and Jagannath Temple, Museums including Salar Jung Museum, TS State Archaeology Museum and Birla Science Museum, Parks & Lakes including NTR Gardens, Lumbini Park, Mahavir Harina Vanasthali National Park and Mrugavani National Park, Recreational Places including Shilparamam, Shilpakala Vedika, and Jalavihar.

II. METHODOLOGY

To identify and establish gender-sensitive tourism indicators for the research, an internet-based questionnaire survey (Expert Opinion survey) was designed for a total of 41 experts comprising 23 females and 19 males’ based on their areas of specialization, familiarity with the research, and expertise in the field of tourism, gender, urban planning, and related fields respectively. The Survey Questionnaire was framed under the ‘5 Point Likert Scale’ which initially rated 36 sub-attributes that had been extracted and identified from literature studies under 3 main attributes namely economic, social, and environmental aspects. Apart from these questions, the questionnaire also included a few open-ended questions such as opinions on any existing social, economic, or environmental framework or policy to assess gender-sensitive tourism at the national or international level, challenges to mainstream gender inclusion in tourism, presence of gender-sensitive indicators at the national or international level, etc. Based on the inferences, a final questionnaire was prepared to incorporate the 36 sub-attributes under 3 main attributes (see Table 1).

Table 1 Details of Attributes and Sub-Attributes

Economic Indicators	Workforce Participation Wage gap	Income & Expenditure	Working Conditions Employment – full-time/ part-time/ Number/Informal work	Occupational health, segregation	Rating
Social Indicators	Safety- Streetlights Signage- directional/shop Tourist Helpline/	Accessibility & Mobility- Road Connectivity/ Approach Road	Tourist Amenities- Potable Drinking Water Provision of Dustbins Public Toilets Eating Points/ Quality	Transportation Infrastructure- Accessibility of tourist sites by Public transport Provision of Bus	Rating

	Time & Distance covered to access tourist site Surrounding Land use Existing safety standards	Quality of Roads Public Convenience along roads Wayside Amenities Last-mile connectivity to tourist site	Street Vending/Souvenir Shops Number/% of tourism establishments complying with safety and security standards. Availability of budget/luxury hotels Availability of tourist guidance/reception centers	Stations/Cab stations Road Map/Signage Map Well-lit and surveilled parking spaces Level of Pedestrian Infrastructure Availability of alternate modes of transport-taxi, auto, mass transit system	
Environmental Indicators	Cleanliness in and around the site Pollution-air, water, noise	Water Quality/Conservation of heritage sites/monuments		Maintenance & management of tourist site	Rating

Source- Author (2022)

Initially, the sample adequacy was evaluated by Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett Test, where the adequacy is tested, if the 'P' value is less than or = .05. The expert opinion questionnaire was then put to Factor Analysis for identifying the factors affecting the gender inequities and prioritizing the attributes at the selected Tourist sites in the study area. Factor analysis is a technique that is used to reduce a large number of variables into fewer numbers of factors. This technique extracts the maximum common variance from all variables and puts them into a common score. As an index of all variables, we can use this score for further analysis. Factor analysis can be used for the identification of groups of interrelated variables, to see how they are related to each other, and also to identify the hidden dimensions or constructs which may or may not be apparent from the direct analysis. The statistical value computed from the data was 0.745. From the correlation coefficient, it may be concluded that the validity of the questionnaire turns out to be reliable and the flow of questions framed in the questionnaire has a good association among the variables and seems to be understood very well by the respondents. The factor analysis was further carried out using the principal component analysis method. The final data set was analyzed which reveals 3 components accounting for around 68.320% of the variance in data. The selected factors or parameters were used for further analysis and findings of the tourist sites in the study area which are deemed necessary for defining gender-sensitive tourism indicators.

A Simple Random Sampling method was adopted for conducting the primary survey for the tourists (visitor survey), wherein the perceptions of 211 tourists including both men and women were collected from the 16 tourist sites within Hyderabad. The questionnaire comprised 3 sections namely- A demographic profile including the

visitor's name, age, gender, average monthly income, occupational status, educational status, etc. Tourist profile or Travel Information including the purpose of their visit, the average length of their stay, average expenditure incurred on a visit, the most preferred mode of travel, and gender-sensitive tourism infrastructure in and around the sites is further sub-divided into social indicators including safety and security, accessibility, mobility and transportation aspects and environmental indicators including maintenance in and around the site, cleanliness, conservation of heritage monuments respectively.

Apart from the tourist's perception of gender sensitivity, it was equally imperative to capture the opinion of various stakeholders who were employed on the tourist site to assess gender inclusiveness in tourism. Therefore, another set of primary surveys comprising 63 stakeholders including both men and women employees was conducted at each 16 tourist sites. The stakeholders comprised the site manager, maintenance staff including sweepers, gardeners, tour guides, accounts personnel, purchase and stores staff, security personnel, and front office respectively. The stakeholder's survey questionnaire comprised the economic indicators primarily to understand the tourism demand and supply. It was categorized into two sections, first, the Demographic profile including name, age, gender, and employment type, and second, the economic profile including employment details such as total number of employees, number of permanent and contract employees, average monthly income, years of job in service, working hours, existing government schemes for women in tourism, etc. While, for the demographic data, the Chi-square test has been conducted to know whether these attributes differ significantly or not by constructing cross-tabulation among various attributes.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The goodness of all the variables using Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient was tested using the Reliability Analysis. The reliability of any given measurement refers to the consistent measure of Cronbach’s Alpha, which is one way of measuring the strength of that consistency.

Table 2 Chi-Square Test

S. No	Attributes Tested	d.f.	Chi-square Value	P value	Significant/Non-Significant
1	Gender vs Household Size	2	0.506	0.777	Non-Significant
2	Gender vs Mother Tongue	6	8.272	0.219	Non-Significant
3	Gender vs District	16	20.399	0.203	Non-Significant
4	Gender vs Occupational Status	6	34.548	0	Significant
5	Gender vs Marital status	2	4.04	0.133	Non-Significant
6	Gender vs Educational status	5	18.679	0.002	Significant
7	Age vs Household size	10	22.518	0.013	Significant
8	Age vs Mother Tongue	30	26.037	0.673	Non-Significant
9	Age vs District	80	106.065	0.027	Significant
10	Age vs Occupational status	30	181.869	0	Significant
11	Age vs Marital status	10	143.078	0	Significant
12	Age vs Educational status	25	91.954	0	Significant
13	Avg. Monthly Income vs Household size	6	2.795	0.834	Non-Significant
14	Avg. Monthly Income vs Mother Tongue	15	16.909	0.324	Non-Significant
15	Avg. Monthly Income vs District	15	36.329	0.592	Non-Significant
16	Avg. Monthly Income vs Occupational status	18	30.282	0.385	Non-Significant
17	Avg. Monthly Income vs Marital status	6	4.745	0.577	Non-Significant
18	Avg. Monthly Income vs Educational status	15	25.401	0.045	Significant

< P= 0.05 Significant
Source- Author (2022)

From the above table (Table-1) where various attributes have been tested by Chi-Square Goodness of Fit and listed for 18 pairs of attributes, it has been found that out of these 18 pairs, 8 pairs namely gender vs occupational status, educational status, age vs district, occupational status, marital status, educational status and Average monthly income vs educational status are significant with a probability value < or = 0.05 level of significance (LOS), indicating that the attributes are significantly different in the primary data and represents a difference amongst them, while the other 10 attributes tested are non-significant with a probability value greater than 0.05.

After performing the Chi-square test, a multivariate test (Factor Analysis) has been computed for the data. Also for the data, KMO & Bartlett test (Table-2) was performed for data adequacy, and found that the data collected was good enough to use the test. Also, a scree plot (Figure-1) was computed to find out how many components are enough

to represent, and the extraction of the components was also done.

Table 3 KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.502
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	158.047
	df	3
	Sig.	.000

Source- Author (2022)

From the above table (Table-2), the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) Statistic is computed for the Suitability and Sample Adequacy of the data. In the above case, the KMO measure of sampling adequacy computed is 0.502. Bartlett’s test of Sphericity tests the hypothesis of the population correlation matrix vis a vis its identity matrix.

Fig 1 Scree Plot of Factors
Source- Author (2022)

The graphical representation of the components extracted has been shown in the above scree plot (Figure-1). The Scree plot displays the number of the factors with their corresponding eigenvalue. In the above case, the scree plot explains the first six factors for the Total Variability in data.

Table 4 Total Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.267	20.420	20.420	3.267	20.420	20.420	3.071	19.193	19.193
2	2.895	18.092	38.511	2.895	18.092	38.511	2.450	15.311	34.504
3	2.056	12.850	51.362	2.056	12.850	51.362	2.357	14.729	49.232
4	1.313	8.205	59.567	1.313	8.205	59.567	1.361	8.505	57.737
5	1.150	7.186	66.753	1.150	7.186	66.753	1.326	8.288	66.025
6	1.039	6.496	73.250	1.039	6.496	73.250	1.156	7.225	73.250
7	.977	6.105	79.355	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	.869	5.432	84.788	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	.722	4.512	89.299	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	.567	3.546	92.845	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	.392	2.453	95.298	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	.311	1.945	97.243	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	.228	1.423	98.666	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	.213	1.334	100.000	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	-8.552E-17	-5.345E-16	100.000	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	-3.317E-16	-2.073E-15	100.000	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: using Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis, Author (2022)

In the above table (Table-3), to meet the objective of identifying the factors affecting the gender inequities in the Tourist sites in Hyderabad, the Factor Analysis method has been carried out by Varimax Rotation Matrix Method. In Factor Analysis, the Principal Component Analysis method was implemented for the Dimension Reduction and Identification of the Significant Factors for assessing gender sensitivity in tourism. Here, the 16 attributes were further reduced and distributed to 6 meaningful factors by factor analysis. The 6 components are extracted with an overall response of 73.25%.

Table 5 Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix						
	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Type_of_Traveller_Visitor_TI	-.076	.111	-.162	.849	.009	-.166
Age_group_TI	.776	.194	-.261	-.003	-.110	-.113
Perpose_of_Visit_TI	-.012	-.050	.038	-.149	-.023	.938
Source_of_Information_TI	.763	.117	-.002	-.316	.048	-.251
Average_length_stay_TI	.200	.550	.076	-.130	.355	.060
Influence_Gender_Sensitivity_TI	.721	-.239	.319	.101	.093	.096
willingness_to_spend_on_trip_TI	-.272	.045	.280	-.090	.436	-.137
Mode_of_Travel_within_city_TI	-.513	-.088	.408	-.159	.028	-.328
Public_pvt_More_Gender_Sensitive_TI	.584	.065	.101	.551	-.269	.044
First_Visit_To_tour_Site_TI	-.064	-.272	-.159	.167	-.697	.008
If_No_Number_of_Times_Visited_in_Past_TI	.763	.017	-.059	.049	.223	.146
Reason_For_Frequent_Visit_TI	-.018	.124	.953	-.066	.068	.029
Time_of_visit_TI	-.018	.124	.953	-.066	.068	.029
Maximum_expenditure_of_Tourist_TI	-.001	.967	.085	.103	.002	-.050
Behaviour_of_Staff_TI	-.001	.967	.085	.103	.002	-.050
Distance_from_location_of_Stay_TI	.234	-.189	-.194	.307	.607	.062
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.						
a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.						

Source- Author (2022)

From the above table (Table-4), it may be concluded that Factor 1(mode of travel) contained 6 sub-attributes, explaining 20.42% of the variance and an Eigenvalue of 3.267. The sub-attributes include age group, source of information, the influence of gender sensitivity on the stay, mode of travel within the city, public or private mode of travel is gender-sensitive, and the number of times visited site in the past. Factor 2 (visitor stay) contained 3 sub-attributes, explaining 18.092% of the variance and an Eigenvalue of 2.895. The sub-attributes included average length of stay, average expenditure, and behavior of staff. Factor 3 (visitor travel) contained 2 sub-attributes, explaining 12.85% of the variance and Eigenvalue of 2.056. The sub-attributes include the reason for the frequent visits and the time of the visit. Factor 4 (visitor type) contained only 1 sub-attribute, explaining 8.205% of the variance and Eigenvalue of 1.313. The sub-attribute includes the type of visitor. Factor 5 (visitor's expenditure) contained only 3 sub-attribute, explaining 7.186% of the variance and Eigenvalue of 1.150. The sub-attribute included the willingness to spend, the first visit to the site, and distance from the location of stay. Factor 6 (visitor's purpose of travel) contained only 1 sub-attribute, explaining 6.496% of the variance and Eigenvalue of 1.039. The sub-attribute includes the purpose of the visit. Hence, these six components derived are as follows- mode of travel, visitor stay, visitor travel, visitor type, visitor's expenditure, and visitor's purpose of travel.

IV. CONCLUSION

Globally all policies recognize and emphasize the need for a concerted focus on an inclusive urban society. To reduce gender inequality, it becomes imperative to mainstream gender in the development of an economy and particularly in the tourism policy framework,

programs/schemes at both the Central and State level. Therefore, an institutional mechanism needs to be planned out to ensure effective implementation of Gender Responsive Planning & Budgeting (GRB) and strategizing ways to integrate a gender-inclusive perspective across the planning, budgeting, implementation, monitoring, and auditing continuum which provides the opportunity for purposive gender responsive planning within the tourism sector or subsector in Hyderabad.

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